

KonsortSWD

Konsortium für die
Sozial-, Verhaltens-, Bildungs- und
Wirtschaftswissenschaften

**Gute Daten.
Bessere Forschung!**

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Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17453425>

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In Zusammenarbeit mit

nfdi

TA.2-M.1: Support CoreTrustSeal

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Organisational Infrastructure

- **R0. Background Information & Context (R0)**
- **Mission & Scope (R01)**
R01. The repository has an explicit mission to provide access to and preserve digital objects.
- **Rights Management (R02)**
R02. The repository maintains all applicable rights and monitors compliance.
- **Continuity of Service (R03)**
R03. The Repository has a plan to ensure ongoing access to and preservation of its data and metadata.
- **Legal & Ethical (R04)**
R04. The repository ensures to the extent possible that data and metadata are created, curated, preserved, accessed and used in compliance with legal and ethical norms.
- **Governance & Resources (R05)**
R05. The repository has adequate funding and sufficient numbers of staff managed through a clear system of governance to effectively carry out the mission.
- **Expertise & Guidance (R06)**
R06. The repository adopts mechanisms to secure ongoing expertise, guidance and feedback-either in-house, or external.

Digital Object Management

- **Provenance and authenticity (R07)**
R07. The repository guarantees the authenticity of the digital objects and provides provenance information.
- **Deposit & Appraisal (R08)**
R08. The repository accepts data and metadata based on defined criteria to ensure relevance and understandability for users.
- **Preservation plan (R09)**
R09. The repository assumes responsibility for long-term preservation and manages this function in a planned and documented way.
- **Quality Assurance (R10)**
R10. The repository addresses technical quality and standards compliance and ensures that sufficient information is available for end users to make quality-related evaluations.
- **Workflows (R11)**
R11. Digital object management takes place according to defined workflows from deposit to access.
- **Discovery and Identification (R12)**
R12. The repository enables users to discover the digital objects and refer to them in a persistent way through proper citation.
- **Reuse (R13)**
R13. The repository enables reuse of the digital objects over time, ensuring that appropriate information is available to support understanding and use.

Information Technology & Security

- **Storage & Integrity (R14)**
R14. The repository applies documented processes to ensure data and metadata storage and integrity.
- **Technical Infrastructure (R15)**
R15. The repository is managed on well-supported operating systems and other core infrastructural software and hardware appropriate to the services it provides to its Designated Community.
- **Security (R16)**
R16. The repository protects the facility and its data, metadata, products, services, and users.

Reihenfolge der Requirements im Rahmen der Arbeitsgruppe

Aufgrund der unterschiedlichen Komplexitätsgrade wurden die Requirements nicht gemäß der numerischen Abfolge bearbeitet, sondern nach der von uns angenommenen Schwierigkeit und den notwendigen Hilfestellungen durch Leitung, andere Abteilungen oder Partner.

einfach

mittel schwer

Ro

Background Information & Context

Ro. Background Information & Context

1. Re3data Identifier.

2. Repository type.

- Select a repository type: Specialist repositories are asked to provide their domain(s) and/or discipline(s).

See glossary (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051124>, 25.09.2025)

3. Overview.

- short overview of **key characteristics** of the repository, reflecting the repository type.
 - **scope**
 - **size** of data collections
 - data **types**
 - data **formats**
 - Further **contextual information** (not covered elsewhere)

4. Designated Community.

- Guidance:

- A clear definition of the **Designated Community** or 'sub-communities'
 - **composition, skills, knowledge** base, and needs, and how these may **transform over time**
 - understanding of typical **re-use scenarios** and purposes
 - how the applicant monitors and **responds to changes in the needs** of the Designated Community.
 - applicants should explicitly state any **tacit assumptions**, such as (foreign) language skills, ability to access specific Operating Systems or Internet browsers, use certain software, and so on.

5. Levels of Curation.

Select all relevant types from:

- A. Content distributed as deposited
 - B. Basic curation – e.g. brief checking, addition of basic metadata or documentation
 - C. Enhanced curation – e.g. conversion to new formats during ingest, enhancement of documentation and metadata
 - D. Data-level curation – as in C above, but with additional editing of deposited data
- long-term accessibility and understandability of data is less likely at curation levels A or B, [...]
 - For each level selected add some concise information e.g. automatic checks of metadata, intellectual checks and editing of documentation, file format identification, transformation to preservation file formats, etc.
 - When more than one level,
 - further information to be added on the proportion of the data in the collection curated to the respective levels.
 - state any relevant differences in workflows or employed measures for each selected curation level.
 - higher level of formal provenance, integrity, and version management (change logs, etc.) for more curation levels
 - All levels of curation assume
 - (1) initial deposits are retained unchanged and edits are only made on copies
 - (2) metadata enables to understand and use the data independently
 - (3) ongoing measures for active preservation are in place for greater part of the collection(s).
 - demonstrate that
 - any (meta)data annotations/edits are undertaken and documented by appropriate experts and
 - the integrity of all original copies is maintained.

6. Cooperation and outsourcing to third parties, partners and host organisations.

- If for one or more requirements the applicant is supported by another organization in making decisions or taking actions, document
 - **function** or service
 - the **nature of the relationship** or agreement (contractual, Service Level Agreement, Memorandum of Understanding, etc.)
 - relevant **certifications**
- Such relationships may include but are not limited to **cooperation** or federation with other repositories, any **services** provided by an institution the applicant is part of, **storage** provided by others as part of multi-copy redundancy, or organisations that may undertake some responsibility for data, metadata and services in a **service continuity or succession** situation.
- The listed organisations should then be **clearly referenced** under each relevant Requirement
- **details are essential** to ensure a comprehensive review process (e.g. provide appropriate evidence for shared responsibility)
- CoreTrustSeal applicant must retain **responsibility for the preservation planning** and actions undertaken to data and metadata to ensure they remain usable by their Designated Community for the long term.
- a **context diagram** (e.g. the OAIS functional model) is useful

■ *Guidance*

- "If the applicant is **entirely responsible** for all decisions and takes all relevant actions related to meeting each of the 16 Requirements then **this section can be left blank**. If for one or more requirements the applicant is supported by another organization in making decisions or taking actions, that organisation, the role it plays, and its relationship with the applicant should be listed here."
- "If a **repository function** and/or supporting evidence that is **covered by the CoreTrustSeal is not under the direct control of the applicant**, then the relevant host organisation, partner or other third party should be listed here. "

Frage zum Review: Wie weit sind die genannten Kooperationen zu fassen?

- Serviceprovider für den täglichen Betrieb?
- Arbeitsgruppen?
- Zusammenschlüsse?
- VerbundFDB, RatSWD, KonsortSWD, NFDI, ...

R05

Governance & Resources

R05. The repository has adequate **funding** and sufficient numbers of **staff** managed through a clear system of **governance** to effectively carry out the mission.

- Descriptions and **diagrams** of governance bodies, groups and hierarchies.
- Timescales for provision and **renewal of funding** for operational costs and recruitment (it is understood that permanent, ongoing funding cannot be perfectly quantified or guaranteed – **transparency** is key)
- Evidence as **recognized institution** by the Designated Community
- Demonstrate that the repository can **meet its obligations**, including sufficient funding, staff resources, IT resources, and a budget for external engagement when necessary.
- Other relevant information could include
 - balance of **structural** versus **project** funding,
 - the total number of full time equivalent (**FTE**) employees,
 - the proportions of staff employed on a **permanent** or **temporary basis**.

R12

Discovery and Identification

R12. The repository enables users to **discover** the digital objects and refer to them in a **persistent way** through proper **citation**.

- The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:
 - The **search facilities** offered by the repository.
 - The **metadata standards** that a searchable metadata catalogue complies with.
 - The approach to ensuring that **identifiers** are **unique and persistent**
 - **version rules**
 - **Machine harvesting** of the metadata
 - inclusion in disciplinary or generic **registries** of resources.
 - **Attribution** and **citation guidance**
- The use of a third party to support PID creation and resolution is not sufficient; applicants should describe how they **ensure that identifiers continue to resolve to the correct data or metadata over time**
 - *DataCite: "The DataCite link checker service is a custom-built web crawler that periodically checks a random sampling of DOIs to verify that they still resolve to a valid URL" <https://support.datacite.org/docs/link-checker> (25.09.2025)*
 - *GESIS CoreTrustSeal Certification about da|ra: "A DOI is registered for all published data sets via the da|ra registration agency. [...] The da|ra system will send automatic notifications in case DOIs no longer resolve so that the issue can be investigated." <https://doi.org/10.34894/Y5YJGK> (25.09.2025)*

Ro6

Expertise & Guidance

Ro6. The repository adopts mechanisms to secure **ongoing expertise, guidance and feedback** -either in-house, or external.

- **identify the skills necessary** to deliver the services it offers, and source and maintain those skills (internal resources or external engagement)
- strive to **accommodate evolutions** (data types, data volumes, new technologies) to remain valuable to its Designated Community.
- The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:
 - That guidance and expertise reflects the **scientific scope** of the repository, if relevant.
 - The **expertise**, including any relevant affiliations (e.g. national or international bodies), is **appropriate to the mission**.
 - Repository has **sufficient internal expertise**
 - Staff
 - The repository aligns internal **recruitment** and external engagement with the services it offers.
 - The repository ensures that its **staff** have access to **ongoing training** and professional **development**.
 - The repository is linked to a **wide network** for advice and guidance (In-house **advisers**, or external advisory committees incl. technical, curation, data science, data security, and disciplinary **experts**)
 - Show how you **communicate with experts for advice**.
- Evidence must account for
 - the repository **day-to-day activities** and
 - the **monitoring** of potential **new challenges** on the horizon (community and technology watch).

Welche Fähigkeiten werden allgemein benötigt? Fachlich, IT, Management, Rechtliches, ...

Show your **inhouse skills** as well as your **wide network**

Provide evidence from **day-to-day** business and **monitoring** new challenges

Ausbildung (fachlicher Scope), Einarbeitungskonzept, FDM, Datenschutz, Publikationen und Vorträge (auch zu FDM), Verweis auf Personalentwicklungskonzept

Beirat/Kuratorium/Gremium/FDI Ausschuss, Netzwerke, KonsortSWD, VerbundFDB, ...
Ext. Beratung zu rechtlichen oder technischen Aspekten

RO2

Rights Management

R02. The repository maintains all applicable **rights** and monitors **compliance**.

- The repository **manages, and communicates** to relevant stakeholders, all **rights** (permissions, prohibitions, obligations) covering data and metadata deposit, storage, preservation, access, and use (e.g. licenses, agreements, terms and conditions, and related policies and procedures) in place for rights management.
- The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:
 - The overall **rights management approach** to deposited files, data and metadata.
 - Deposit and access **agreements** or licenses.
 - The rights from the **depositor** to copy, transform, and store digital objects for preservation, as well as provide access to them
 - Conditions of **use** (e.g. intellectual property rights, distribution, intended use, protection of sensitive data, etc.).
 - For sensitive data, in particular, licences may specify **limitations on use, usage environment** (safe room, secure remote access), and types of users (approved researcher, minimum training requirements, etc.).
 - How **rights metadata** is managed for humans (e.g. license documents/files) or machines.
 - include **obligations such as citation and attribution of data and metadata**
 - access without any conditions should be made clear in the response statement as well
 - Monitoring of **compliance** at deposit, during curation/preservation, and during access and reuse. Describe any circumstances where compliance monitoring is not possible.
 - Measures in place if **non-compliance** is detected.
 - While it may be challenging to identify instances of noncompliance, consideration should be given to the consequences if noncompliance is detected e.g. **sanctions** on current or future access/use of data and metadata.
 - In the case of sensitive personal data disclosure, there may be severe legal penalties that impact both the user and repository. Ideally, repositories should have a public policy in place for noncompliance.

1. Datenaufnahme
2. Datennutzung
3. Metadaten
4. Zitation etc.
5. Compliance
6. Non-Compliance

Metadaten sollten eine (öffentlich zugängliche) Lizenz haben

GESIS gutes Beispiel

RO4

Legal & Ethical

RO4. The repository ensures [...] that data and metadata are created, curated, preserved, accessed and used in compliance with **legal and ethical norms**.

Datenschutz,
Urheberrecht, ...

1. Relevante Rechtsbereiche / ethische Praktiken
2. Informationen von Datengebern
3. Umgang mit sensiblen Daten

- awareness and processes around **legal and ethical** issues, including **privacy and confidentiality**, that impact the creation, curation, and use of digital objects.
- Evidence should demonstrate that the applicant **understands their legal environment** and the relevant **ethical practices**, and that they have **documented procedures** in place to ensure conformity.
- The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:
 - **How the repository identifies and manages** relevant legal and ethical standards that impact operations.
 - Compliance with **specific legal and/or ethical discipline** or **domain standards**.
 - **Information requested from depositors** to confirm that data collection or creation was carried out in accordance with legal and ethical criteria in the relevant geographical location or discipline (e.g. Ethical Review Committee/Institutional Review Board).
 - Any data or metadata with disclosure risk e.g. depositor/**user information**, personal, cultural, or environmental information
- For applicants that hold data or metadata with **disclosure risk** include references to the following items:
 - Special procedures applied to manage disclosure risk
 - **Conditions** of distribution, **access protection** and use
 - Processes to review disclosure risk and to take the necessary steps to either **anonymize** files or to provide access in a **secure way**
 - **Staff training** in the management of digital objects with disclosure risk.
 - Guidance provided on the **responsible deposit**, download, and use of disclosive or potentially disclosive data and metadata.
- **Disclosure risk**: the repository must take **appropriate measures** to ensure they are dealt with in accordance with legal regulations.

R13

Reuse

R13. The repository enables **reuse** over time, ensuring that information is available to support **understanding** and use.

Daten und Metadaten bleiben verständlich über techn. Wandel und Änderungen bei der Designated Community

1. Kontakt mit Designated Community
2. Standards wie Dateiformate, Metadaten schemata, Vokabulare
3. Metadaten/Dokumentation
4. Umgang mit Änderungen

AUSSDA gutes Beispiel (strukturiert entlang des Requirements)

- Repositories must ensure that **data and metadata continue to be understood** despite changes in **technology** and the **Designated Community's knowledge base**.
- This Requirement evaluates the measures taken to **ensure that data and metadata are reusable**.
 - The ways in which the repository **engages with their Designated Community** of users to identify their needs.
 - The data **formats, metadata schemas, controlled vocabularies** and how these meet the **community needs**.
 - The metadata and **documentation provided at the point of access** to the Designated Community.
 - Measures to ensure that data and metadata **remain understandable**.
 - Management of **changes to data, metadata**, documentation or other information that supports reuse.
- Responses to this Requirement should **focus on engagement with the Designated Community**, identification of their needs and specifying how their needs are met.
- Responses and evidence should demonstrate both an **in-depth knowledge of reuse scenarios and the needs of the Designated Community** in terms of their practices, technical environment, and (adherence to) applicable standards.
- **Changes in technology and in the methodologies** and norms employed by the Designated Community can lead to a need to change the structure, content or delivery mechanisms for data and metadata. Appropriate, high-quality metadata conforming to a general and/or disciplinary-specific schema should be referred to in the evidence provided. This information is critical to the design curation processes that ensure digital objects remain understandable over time and usable by the Designated Community.

R08

Deposit & Appraisal

Ro8. The repository accepts (meta)data based on defined **criteria** to ensure **relevance and understandability** for users.

- Eingang prüfen
 1. Inhaltlich (Collection Policy, Dokumentation)
 2. Technisch (Dateiformate, techn. Eigenschaften)
 3. (rechtlich)
- (Meta)daten sind verständlich – jetzt und in Zukunft
- Dateiformate definieren

- The **appraisal** function during deposit is critical
 - to evaluate whether digital objects meet all **criteria for selection** and
 - to ensure appropriate management for their **preservation**
 - documented deposit process that includes steps to ensure that **data and metadata are sufficient for long-term preservation**.
- **collection development policy** or procedures to guide the selection of digital objects.
 - **Criteria for prioritisation** and any different curation-levels or preservation levels defined during appraisal.
 - The approach to digital objects that do not fall within the mission/collection profile.
 - For the collection to remain relevant to and usable, **selection criteria may have to be revised** (changes in technology, culture, or legislation (e.g., data protection or intellectual property rights))
- Metadata
 - Procedures to determine that the **metadata required to interpret and use** the digital objects are provided.
 - Any automated **assessment** of metadata adherence to relevant schemas.
 - The repository approach if metadata provided is **insufficient for long-term preservation**.
- List of **preferred formats**.
 - Checks in place to ensure that depositors adhere to the preferred formats.
 - The approach towards digital objects that are deposited in non-preferred formats.
- Repository staff should have all the necessary information, procedures, and expert knowledge to ensure long-term preservation and use as applicable to the **Designated Community**.

Langzeitarchivierung (LZA) - Definition

Langzeit

„[...] bedeutet für die Bestandserhaltung digitaler Ressourcen nicht die Abgabe einer Garantieerklärung über fünf oder fünfzig Jahre, sondern die verantwortliche *Entwicklung von Strategien*, die den *beständigen*, vom Informationsmarkt verursachten *Wandel bewältigen* können.“

Liegmann, Hans; Neuroth, Heike (2010)

Archivierung

„bedeutet [...] *mehr als nur die dauerhafte Speicherung* digitaler Informationen auf einem Datenträger. Vielmehr schließt es die *Erhaltung* der dauerhaften *Verfügbarkeit* und damit eine *Nachnutzung* und *Interpretierbarkeit* der digitalen Ressourcen mit ein.“

Liegmann, Hans; Neuroth, Heike (2010)

Ebenen der Langzeitarchivierung

„[...] Verfügbarkeit und damit eine Nachnutzung und Interpretierbarkeit [...]“

Entwicklung von Strategien, die den [...] Wandel bewältigen können.“

Grafik basierend auf:

Thibodeau, Kenneth. (2002). Overview of Technological Approaches to Digital Preservation and Challenges in Coming Years. In Council on Library and Information Resources (Ed.), The state of digital preservation: An international perspective; conference proceedings, Documentation Abstracts, Inc. Institutes for Information Science, Washington, D.C., April 24-25, 2002 (pp. 4-31). CLIR. <https://www.clir.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/6/pub107.pdf> (25.09.2025)

Collection Policy

Beispielhafte Struktur

Einleitung

Diese Collection Policy legt die Richtlinien und Verfahren fest, die für die Sammlung, Veröffentlichung und Archivierung von Daten in [...] gelten. Ziel ist es, die Integrität, Zugänglichkeit und den langfristigen Erhalt der Daten zu gewährleisten.

Zweck der Sammlung

Die Sammlung von Daten dient folgenden Zwecken:

- Bereitstellung von Daten für die Öffentlichkeit und die wissenschaftliche Gemeinschaft
- Sicherstellung der Einhaltung gesetzlicher und regulatorischer Anforderungen
- und weitere...

Kriterien für die Sammlung

Die folgenden Kriterien müssen erfüllt sein, um Daten in das Archiv aufzunehmen:

- Relevanz: Die Daten müssen für das Forschungsfeld von Bedeutung sein
- Qualität: Die Daten müssen den Qualitätsstandards genügen
- Rechtmäßigkeit: Die Sammlung muss im Einklang mit geltenden Gesetzen und Vorschriften stehen.

Datentypen (*Beispiel DZHW*)

Zum Profil gehören sowohl Daten aus quantitativen als auch Daten aus qualitativen Erhebungen, derzeit primär Survey-Daten, Analyseskripte und zugehörige -daten sowie Interviewtranskripte, ggf. auch gekoppelt in Mixed-Methods-Studien. Erweiterungen um weitere Arten von Daten sind mittelfristig angedacht. Sofern ein Forschungsprojekt weitere Datentypen archivieren möchte, kann die Machbarkeit mit dem FDZ-DZHW gemeinsam eruiert werden

Zugriff und Nutzung

- Der Zugriff auf die Daten erfolgt nur für autorisierte Benutzer*innen
- Die Nutzung der Daten muss den festgelegten Richtlinien entsprechen

Überprüfung und Aktualisierung der Policy

Diese Collection Policy wird regelmäßig überprüft und bei Bedarf aktualisiert, um sicherzustellen, dass sie den aktuellen rechtlichen und technologischen Anforderungen entspricht.

Beispiele:

GESIS: https://www.gesis.org/fileadmin/admin/Dateikatalog/Publicationen/Sonstiges/20230525_datenservice_collectionpolicy_de.pdf (25.09.2025)

FDZ am IQB (Collection Policy des VerbundFDB: https://www.forschungsdaten-bildung.de/fileadmin/FDB/Downloads/How-to_Daten-teilen/VerbundFDB_Collection-Policy.pdf (25.09.2025))

Metadaten für die Langzeitarchivierung

Tabelle 1: Metadatenklassen für die Erhaltung⁴⁰

deskriptiv	Bibliographische Angaben, z. B. Titel, Autor*in sowie inhaltliche Angaben, z. B. Abstract, Erhebungsmethode
strukturell	Angaben zum Gesamtzusammenhang des archivierten Informationsobjektes, z. B. Beziehung von Dateien zueinander
administrativ	Informationen zum Archivierungsprozess, z. B. rechtlich (Lizenzen, Verträge, Zugangsrechte, Urheberrecht, ...), Provenienz (Entstehung, Dateihistorie, Bearbeiter*in, ...)
technisch	Großteiles automatisierte Metadaten, z. B. Dateiformate, Originalpfade, Dateigröße, Versionen, Größen, Checksummen

Quelle:

Hoffstätter, U., & Weber, A. (2024). Langzeitarchivierung von Forschungsdaten. Einführung in das Thema zu Daten der Sozial-, Verhaltens-, Bildungs- und Wirtschaftswissenschaften in Forschungsdatenzentren. KonsortSWD Working Paper Nr.9/2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10418834> (25.09.2025)

Metadaten für die Langzeitarchivierung

Metadatenklassen

- Deskriptive Metadaten
 - Dublin Core (da|ra, DataCite) plus semistruktr. Metadaten wie Daten- und Methodenberichte etc.
- Technische Metadaten
 - Dateiname
 - ursprünglicher Pfad
 - Dateigröße
 - Dateiformat
 - Prüfsummen
 - Ergebnisse des Virustests
- Strukturelle Metadaten
 - Kollektion: IsVersionOf, ...
 - Dateien: Beziehung zw. Dateien
- Administrative Metadaten
 - Provenienz (Erstellung, Erwerb)
 - zur Erhaltung getroffenen Maßnahmen (Software, Audit Trail)
 - PID
 - vertragliche Vereinbarungen zur Archivierung
 - Informationen über Rechte

Digital Asset Register - Template

Kollektions-/ Studienebene

Da|ra / DataCite

weitere Metadaten (u. a.) für die LZA

„[...] Verfügbarkeit und damit eine Nachnutzung und Interpretierbarkeit [...]“

AIP-ID	Kollektion/Studie	FDZ Datenkurator*innen	Erhebungen	Datentyp	...	Verantwortliche Person oder Abteilung	Dateiformate	Dateiformat geprüft	Aufbewahrungsrichtlinie - z. B. Wie lange muss dieser Inhalt aufbewahrt werden? Warum?	Urheberrechte, Datenschutzfragen und anderes Rechtliches
nac2018	Nacaps 2018	Schmidtchen, Henrike; Daniel, Andreas;	6	Quantitativ/Survey		Schmidtchen, Henrike	dta 12.0, SPSS 22, csv, docx, PDF/A	ja, DROID 12	Keine Begrenzung	Kein Informed Consent für Gesundheitsdaten
gra2005	DZHW-Absolventenpanel 2005	Baillet, Florence; Franken, Andreas; Weber, Anne	8	Quantitativ/Survey		Weber, Anne	dta 12.0, SPSS 22, csv, docx, PDF/A	nein	Bis Ende 2035	Fragen 1 u. 4 dürfen aus urheherr. Gründen nicht herausgegeben werden

→ Workflow und Verantwortlichen für die Erstellung und Pflege des DAR definieren

Weitere Ressourcen:

Digital Asset Register – Step by step: <https://www.dpconline.org/digipres/implement-digipres/dar-toolkit/dar-stepbystep> (25.09.2025)

DAR template: Digital Preservation Coalition (2024). *Digital Asset Register Toolkit, 1st Edition*, <http://www.doi.org/10.7207/dartool24-01> (25.09.2025)

Dublin Core Metadatenelemente

Inhalt

- 1 contributor
- 2 coverage
- 3 creator
- 4 date
- 5 description
- 6 format
- 7 identifier
- 8 language
- 9 publisher
- 10 relation
- 11 rights
- 12 source
- 13 subject
- 14 title
- 15 type

Quelle: <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dces/> (25.09.2025)

Verifiable File Manifest

Dateiebene

DAP-ID	Dateiname	Pfad	Checksumme	Dateigröße	Dateiformat	Dateiformat geprüft
nac2018	nac2018_p_o_2-0-0.dta	C:\projects\intern\nac2018\v2.0.0\AIP\On-Site	7c9b35da4f2ebd436f		dta 12.0,	ja, DROID 12
nac2018	nac2018_p_r_2-0-0.dta	C:\projects\intern\nac2018\v2.0.0\AIP\Remote-Desktop	1cf88e5a39b3a257ed		dta 12.0	nein
nac2018	nac2018_p_d_2-0-0.dta	C:\projects\intern\nac2018\v2.0.0\AIP\Download-SUF	2e2107b67a1924419			
nac2018	nac2018_p_c_2-0-0.dta	C:\projects\intern\nac2018\v2.0.0\AIP\Download-CUF	6e2107b67a1926661			
nac2018	nac2018_p_c_2-0-0.sav	C:\projects\intern\nac2018\v2.0.0\AIP\sav	f4a22be3c955ac49da		SPSS 22	
nac2018	nac2018_edt_100.dta	C:\projects\intern\nac2018\v2.0.0\AIP\edit\	f4a22be3c955ac49da			
nac2018	nac2018_edt_soc_100.do	C:\projects\intern\nac2018\v2.0.0\AIP\edit\	f5a22be3c955ac49da			
nac2018	nac2018_edt_anony_100.do	C:\projects\intern\nac2018\v2.0.0\AIP\edit\	h4a22be3c955ac49da			
nac2018	nac2018_dmb_2-0-0.docx	C:\projects\intern\nac2018\v2.0.0\AIP\	f4a22be3c955ac49da			
nac2018	nac2018_dmb_2-0-0.pdf	C:\projects\intern\nac2018\v2.0.0\AIP\	f4a22be6c955ac49da			
sid2021	sid2018_edt_100.dta	C:\projects\intern\sid2021\v.1.0.0\AIP\edit\	f4a22bdfsd955ac49da			
sid2021	sid2018_edt_soc_100.do	C:\projects\intern\sid2021\v.1.0.0\AIP\edit\	sdg22be3c955ac49da			
sid2021	sid2018_edt_anony_100.do	C:\projects\intern\sid2021\v.1.0.0\AIP\edit\	fl94dbe3c955ac49da			
sid2021	sid2018_dmb_2-0-0.docx	C:\projects\intern\sid2021\v.1.0.0\AIP\	ifgh4d2be3c955ac49da			
sid2021	sid2018_dmb_2-0-0.pdf	C:\projects\intern\sid2021\v.1.0.0\AIP\	f4a22be3sdhac49da			

➔ Workflow schaffen und dokumentieren

(Beispiel)

Unterschiede DAR und VFM

Digital Asset Register

- Is an **overview** of all **collections**
- allows you to identify the location of each of your digital **collections**
- along with some **high-level metadata** on their condition and status.
- collections **managers** or those responsible for digital preservation systematically record all digital content

Kollektions-/ Studienebene

Verifiable File Manifest

- Is a list of all **files** in each file package and their **location**
- check that all files are still present, and none are damaged (**fixity**)
- is about **file types** and the **size** of data
- used mainly by digital preservation **practitioners**

Dateiebene

Dateiformate – Beispiel GESIS

Art der Daten	Bevorzugte Formate	Akzeptierte Formate
Daten (Statistik-Formate)	Stata (.dta) R (.rds; .rda)	SAS Transport, SAS, SPSS Portable
	Weit verbreitete (proprietäre) Formate von Statistikpaketen, wie z.B. SPSS (.sav), Stata (.dta) Tabulator-, Komma- oder Spalten-getrennte Textdatei ("csv") mit zusätzlicher Setup-Datei (setup, command oder syntax file für SPSS, Stata, SAS usw.) mit entsprechenden Datendefinitionen (Variablenamen u. -label, fehlenden Werten etc.). Alternativ können die Datendefinitionen auch als DDI-XML file übermittelt werden.	OpenDocument-Tabellendokument (*.ods), MS Excel (*.xls, *.xlsx) CSV-Formate ohne zusätzliche Datendefinitionsdateien (Setup, Syntax, Command file) Column Binary-Format (column binary ist ein Standard um Daten als Abbilder von Lochkarten zu repräsentieren) oder Card-Image Format.
Dokumentation (Texte)	PDF/A-1, A-2, A-4 (*.pdf)	OpenDocument Text (*.odt)
	Text-Formate (ASCII, ANSI, etc.)	PDF (*.pdf) MS Word (*.doc, .docx) RichTextFormat (*.rtf) WordPerfect (*.wpd, *.cwp, *.vwp) HTML (*.htm)
Bilder	Baseline TIFF Version 6 unkomprimiert (*.tif)	JPEG 2000
		JPEG, PNG, GIF, BMP PDF/A-1, A-2, A-4, PDF (*.pdf)

Quelle: <https://www.gesis.org/datenservices/ueber-die-datenservices/standards-und-workflows-datenservices/vorbereitung-datenuebergabe-pre-ingest> (25.09.2025)

- sicherstellen, dass die Datengebenden die bevorzugten **Formate einhalten**
 - > Workflow definieren
 - > ggf. mit IT zu Tool zur Erkennung von Dateitypen sprechen
- Umgang mit Dateien, die in nicht diesen Formaten hinterlegt werden
 - > Workflow definieren

RO1

Mission & Scope

R01. The repository has an explicit **mission** to provide access to and **preserve** digital objects.

LZA

Demonstrate publicly that **preservation** (and access) is your **mission**

AUSSDA kompaktes Beispiel

- Repositories take **responsibility** for the curation of digital objects in the appropriate environment for **appropriate periods of time**.
- Thus, **active preservation** of and continued access to the digital objects is an **explicit role of the repository**.
- The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:
 - the **mission** to actively **preserve** and **provide access** to digital objects
 - an **approved public mission statement**,
 - roles **mandated** by funders,
 - or a policy statement signed off by a governing **board**.
- If **preservation** is not referred to **in the mission of the repository** or other relevant public documents provided as evidence, then the compliance level cannot be higher than "In Progress: the repository is in the implementation phase".

RO7

Provenance and authenticity

Digital Object Management

R07. The repository guarantees the **authenticity** of the digital objects and provides **provenance** information

- clear overview of the processes used to ensure data **authenticity** throughout the entire **curation and preservation lifecycle**
- data and metadata management system that maintains **provenance** information to **ensure authenticity** from deposit, and through curation and preservation to access.
 - including the level of **manual and automated practice**.
- Any intentional **changes** to data and metadata should be **documented**, including **the rationale and originator** of the change.
- The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:
 - approach to changing and **versioning data and metadata**.
 - How the approach and records of changes are **communicated to data depositors and users**.
 - The **provenance information** and **audit trails** recorded for data and metadata processing and versioning.
 - How to **compare essential properties** of different versions of the same file.
 - **Identification checks for depositors**.

Authentizität meint die **Echtheit** von Informationen und Quelle (z. B. durch Provenienzinformationen, Dokumentation der Änderungen und Identitätsprüfung)

Provenienz meint die **Herkunft** und den Entstehungsprozess / Lebenszyklus

Herkunft und Authentizität von Dateien und Änderungen von Ingest bis Access
-> Provenance Metadaten
-> Audit Trail / Log File
-> Syntax-Files
-> Versionierung

Beispiel GESIS audit trail:

- name of curator,
- date,
- reason for the change,
- description of the change

Provenienz

Provenienz meint die **Herkunft** und den Entstehungsprozess / Lebenszyklus

Informationen zur Entstehung der Daten

- Creator (DC): wer die Ressource erstellt hat (Einzelperson oder Organisation)
- Contributor (DC): Personen oder Organisationen, die zur Erstellung beigetragen haben.
- Date (DC): z. B. für Erstellungsdatum sowie andere relevante Daten, z. B. Änderungsdaten
- Source (DC): die Ressource stammt oder auf welche andere Ressource sie sich bezieht.
- Relation (DC): Beziehung zu anderen Ressourcen (Verbindungen, Abhängigkeiten)
- Rights (DC): Rechte an der Ressource, einschließlich Urheberrechte und Lizenzen
- Provenance (DCMI): Kommentar Beschreibung aller Änderungen, die an der Ressource vorgenommen wurden (Change Log)
- Herstellungssoftware
- Daten- und Methodenberichte etc.

Standards:

DC / DCMI <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dcmi-terms/>, PROV-DM <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-dm> (25.09.2025)

Authentizität

Authentizität meint die **Echtheit** von Informationen und Quelle (z. B. durch Provenienzinformationen, Dokumentation der Änderungen und Identitätsprüfung)

- Provenienz
- Nachhaltung aller Änderungen (auch seitens Datengebenden)
 - Audit Trails / Log Files
 - Versionierung mit Change Logs
 - Dokumentation ...
- Identität der Datengebenden

Examples

The depositor has permissions to make changes to the record at any time, and assumes responsibility to update a change log.

A relational database maintains a timestamped record of metadata changes, including which staff member applied that change based on their account login.

The data manipulation software used to transform data is saved in a code repository with versioning history. A record of when these routines are applied to a given dataset is retained.

Automated testing ensures that consistent results of a particular data query returns the same product over time, with any discrepancies investigated and rectified or justified as deemed appropriate.

R10

Quality Assurance

R10. The repository addresses **technical quality** and **standards compliance**, and ensures that **sufficient information** is available for end users to make quality-related evaluations.

- 'technical quality' (rather than 'scientific quality'): Quality assurance by the repository ensures that digital objects comply with a range of **standard criteria** including acceptable formats, metadata schema, metadata content and links to other digital objects.
- the repository must ensure there is **sufficient information about the digital objects** for the Designated Community to assess their fitness for use.
- quality issues relevant to their research value does not preclude their use if a user can make a well-informed decision
- The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:
 - The approach to **data and metadata quality** taken by the repository including variations for different **curation-levels**.
 - The **standards** that data, metadata and documentation must comply with.
 - The **quality control checks** in place ensure the completeness and understandability of data and metadata.
 - The **approach to resolving issues** (e.g. returned to the depositor for rectification, fixed by the repository, noted by quality flags, ...).
 - The **approach to managing changes to expected standards** (e.g. new or updated data formats of metadata schemas) in response to changes in the technical environment or to changes in the needs of the Designated Community.
 - **Document** any areas in which data or metadata quality **falls below the expected standard**.
 - **links provided to other digital objects** e.g. related digital objects, publications, or the use of controlled vocabularies and ontologies.
 - How does the repository consider the needs and expectations of the **designated community** regarding quality.

Fokus auf **Aufbereitung/Dokumentation**:

- Anforderungen
 - technisch: Dateiformat, ...
 - inhaltlich: ausreichende Informationen
- **Dokumentationsstandard(s)** (Metadaten, Materialien)
- **Qualitätsprüfung** auf Vollständigkeit und Verständlichkeit
- **Umgang mit Problemen** bei (Meta)Daten
- Erwartungen der Designated Community

- Fokus hier auf *curation*, Verweis möglich auf insb.
 - R08 Deposit & Appraisal (Metadaten, Dateiformate, Kurationsstandards)
 - R07 Provenance & Authenticity (Change Log, Audit Trails ...)
- Qualitätschecks
 - Automatisierte und manuelle **Checks** zur Datenqualität (z. B. Mindestanforderungen entspr. Designated Community, kontrollierte Vokabulare, Pflichtfelder, 4-Augen-Prinzip)
 - (Prüfung des) **Anonymisierungsprozess**
 - **Formatkonvertierung**
 - Umgang mit **Datengebenden** bei (Dokumentation von) Änderungen
 - Informationen zu (abweichenden) Qualitätsstandards
 - Kuratierungslevel beschreiben, falls vorhanden
- **Änderungen von Standards** auf Basis der Designated Community (z. B. weiteres Datenformat und Metadatenfeld)
- Verweis auf **andere Objekte** (z. B. verwandte Daten, Publikationen, Forschungsgruppenoutputs, ...)

Examples

The depositor who enters the metadata and uploads data files is solely responsible for quality assurance, as outlined in their agreement with the repository.

A data curator is assigned to each deposited dataset to **verify** that all required metadata and data content is properly entered and formatted, using a combination of **validation tools and expert judgement**.

The **metadata includes information that influences data quality**, such as measurement accuracy, calibration records and method limitations.

Automated **data assurance checks** are executed for real-time data streams for core instrument types (listed at link). Results are provided in the data files, and curators investigate failures to determine cause and remediation.

R11

Workflows

R11. Digital object management takes place according to defined **workflows** from deposit to access.

- Dokumentation aller Arbeitsabläufe von Datenübergabe bis Datenzugang
- Übersicht wie Workflows an verschiedene Arten von Daten und Metadaten angepasst werden
- Ausführung der Workflows kontrollieren
- Umgang mit Änderungen und Ausnahmen
- Grafiken zur Veranschaulichung nutzen

- Quality Assurance (R10) requires that **workflows** are **defined, documented, and change-managed**.
- Workflows may be specified in a mixture of standard operating procedures (SOP), business process descriptions and diagrams that guide normal practice and provide mechanisms for handling exceptions.
- The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:
 - **Workflows/business process descriptions** covering the curation levels performed.
 - How workflows are **adjusted** for different types of data and metadata.
 - **Decision** handling within the workflows.
 - **Change** management of workflows.
 - Ability to **track** workflow execution, with mechanisms to handle **exceptions**.
- This Requirement confirms that **all workflows are documented**.
- Detailed descriptive workflows may be linked to as evidence if they are public, but this Requirement is seeking **assurance that these workflows exist** and that they are well documented.
- Process **diagrams** or decision trees may be used to **illustrate workflows**. **Highlighting the relationships between processes from the other requirements** can help to explain how individual workflows build into an overall system.
- Details on checks and compliance should be addressed under Quality Assurance (R10).

- Übersicht über Workflows / Dokumentation geben (müssen nicht zwangsläufig alle offen einsehbar sein / verlinkt werden)
- ggf. Grafik/Diagramm als Übersicht

Examples

A recommended workflow is available on our website for depositors to follow, and it is their responsibility to ensure that these steps are taken.

This reference (link here) shows a detailed break-down and diagram of the data ingest workflow, including various pathways for different data types.

On an annual basis, workflows are reviewed and updated to align with any changes in best practices or expectations.

A data curator supports the depositor through the data ingestion workflow, tracking completion of steps and any specific comments along the way.

RO9

Preservation Plan

R09. The repository assumes responsibility for long-term preservation and manages this function in a planned and documented way.

- The repository, depositors, and Designated Community need to understand [the level of responsibility undertaken for the long-term preservation of data and metadata](#). Procedures must be documented and their completion assured.
- The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:
 - The [documented approach to preservation](#), including whether this involves format migration, emulation, etc. [Ensuring bit level integrity is vital but not sufficient for preservation](#).
 - [File formats](#) and [metadata schemas](#) for long term preservation.
 - How the [level of responsibility](#) for the preservation of each item is defined.
 - [Plans related to future migrations](#) or similar measures to address the threat of obsolescence.
 - [Actions](#) relevant to preservation specified in documentation, including custody transfer, submission information criteria, and preservation information metadata.
 - [Measures to ensure these actions are taken](#).
 - Any [minimum stated retention and/or preservation periods](#).
 - [How often the digital objects are re-appraised](#) and the [possible outcomes](#) of reappraisal.
 - The [repository approach to deleting/removing](#) data and metadata from collection/holdings including the impact on persistent identifiers.
- The rights of the repository, including the right to preserve, are covered under Rights Management (R02). Bit level integrity is covered under Storage and Integrity (R14). Acceptable file formats at deposit should be covered under Deposit and Appraisal (R08). Measures to ensure that file formats, schemas and content are appropriate to the Designated Community should be covered under Reuse (R13).

Preservation Plan vs. Preservation Policy

preservation policy	preservation plan
"the big picture"	konkrete Maßnahmen

- Eine Preservation Policy sollte sich möglichst wenig verändern und
 - ein grobes Verständnis für Verantwortlichkeiten klar machen,
 - erläutern, dass man mit Risiken und Anforderungen umgehen kann,
 - betonen, dass man die zukünftige Nutzbarkeit, Verstehbarkeit und Lesbarkeit sicherstellen will.
- Für den Preservation Plan gilt:
 - Beschreibungen nicht überaus detailliert anlegen, damit nicht in engen Abständen aktualisiert werden muss
 - Detailbeschreibungen besser in Arbeitsdokumente auslagern und entsprechend verlinken
 - für manche Institutionen kann es sinnvoll sein, ggf. Plan und Policy in einem Dokument zu sammeln und die Kapitel zu verlinken (es kommt ganz auf den Umfang und die Arbeitsweise an)
- Immer beachten, dass z.B. IQB, AUSSDA und GESIS alle zertifiziert sind und das trotz sehr unterschiedlicher Policies => Bandbreite möglich

Examples

Once a dataset is published, preservation is fully achieved by bit-level verifications on the metadata and data contents.

While submitted data is stored its original form, a conversion to a standardized non-proprietary format is always ensured for interoperable distribution and preservation. The list of preferred formats is available on our website (link here).

The preservation plan (link here) accounts for metadata updates, data format evolution, and technology migrations. Metadata procedures are in place to handle evolving community standards and information availability, such as schema updates (e.g., DataCite schema), controlled vocabularies, or related resources(e.g., publications).

In the rare occasion that access to a dataset is removed, the persistent identifiers can still be resolved with basic descriptive metadata and the rationale for removal (e.g., sensitive data issues or duplication).

R03

Continuity of Service

R03. The Repository has a plan to ensure ongoing access to and preservation of its data and metadata.

The repository must have [measures in place to address the risks inherent in changing circumstances](#), including in mission and/or scope. This Requirement covers the stable management of repository services over time ([business continuity](#)) and the response when services have problems ([disaster recovery](#)). It also includes preparations for handover of digital objects and services to another repository ([succession planning](#)). The [deposit, storage, preservation, and access services](#) offered by the repository to depositors and users are all in scope.

The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:

- The [functions and services offered by the repository](#) to depositors and users.
- The approach to [rapid changes of circumstance](#) and [long-term planning](#).
- The options for [relocation or transition of the activity to another repository](#). For example, the case of cessation of funding due to an unexpected withdrawal of funding, or a shift of host institution interests.
- The repository approach to [managing policies, procedures and other business information over time](#).

Even though succession agreements may be hard to achieve it is important to acknowledge the possibility that a repository will cease to function or exist. [If there is no formal, written agreement between the repository and a successor then the compliance level cannot be higher than "In Progress: the repository is in the implementation phase"](#).

Any technical aspects of business continuity, and disaster and succession planning should be covered in R15 (Technical infrastructure).

Erläuterung aus der Guidance

- Repositories must ensure **continuity of their collections** and assume responsibility in the case of a temporary or permanent break in service. Responses and evidence should demonstrate the **level of responsibility taken for digital objects**, the **level of risk for the repository**, and the **level of succession planning** for the future of the data collection.
- Relevant information could include whether the applicant is the primary or only custodian, whether the depositor shares some responsibility for the future of the digital objects and any service level guarantees or minimum guaranteed time periods (e.g. for retention or preservation) in place.
- If sustainability partially depends on a host or parent organisation, or another organization has guaranteed that it will take over the responsibility in the case of a service discontinuity, this should be clearly indicated. Identifying and entering a formal agreement with a successor organisation that can undertake to deliver the same levels of care and service is acknowledged as a challenge for many repositories. **For this reason a continued status of 'in progress' may be accepted as sufficient during renewal of certification if clearly explained.**
- If there is no formal, written agreement between the repository and a successor organization this requirement cannot be assessed as 'implemented'.

Examples

“In the unlikely event of closure, Repository A will be transferred to National Repository B (link to written agreement).”

“It is unlikely Repository A will ever be closed.”
[without further plans]

“While we deem closure of the repository very unlikely due to steady funding levels and the presence of a parent organisation who are committed to open science, we are working hard on securing an official agreement with this parent organisation.”

Cessation AG von VerbundFDB

- **Was macht die AG?**
 - Aufmerksamkeit auf das Thema lenken
 - Einstieg in die Thematik erleichtern
 - Entwicklung einer gemeinsamen Checkliste, die FDZ Orientierung bietet.
 - Behandlung von Fragen der Datenübergabe und Übertragung der Archivierungsaufgabe als auch von Aspekten der Weiterführung von Services durch andere Repositorien,
- **Beteiligte Institutionen**
 - IQB
 - GESIS
 - DZHW
 - DIPF
- **Aktueller Stand**
 - Eine Anfrage an Lisa Pegelow im Mai ergab, dass eine Einreichung der Arbeitsergebnisse noch im 1. Halbjahr 2025 geplant ist.

R16

Security

R16. The repository **protects** the facility and its data, metadata, products, services, and users.

The repository should **analyze potential threats, assess risks, and create a consistent security system**. It should consider damage scenarios based on malicious actions, human error, or technical failure that pose a threat to the repository and its data, metadata, products, services, and users. It should measure the likelihood and impact of such scenarios, decide **which risk levels are acceptable**, and determine which measures should be taken to counter the threats to the repository and its Designated Community. This should be an ongoing process.

The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:

- The **levels of security** required for different data and metadata and environments, and how these are supported.
- The **IT security system, employees with roles related to security** (e.g. security officers), and any **risk analysis approach in use**.
- Measures in place to **protect the facility**. How the premises where digital objects are held are secured.
- Any **security-specific standards** the repository references or complies with.
- Any **authentication and authorization procedures** employed to securely manage access to systems in use.

Responses should not cover Storage and Integrity (R14) measures or the wider Technical Infrastructure (R15).

Erläuterung aus der Guidance

- Responses and evidence should demonstrate that **the applicant understands all risks to the digital and physical environment** applicable to the service provided to the Designated Community. Mechanisms must be in place to **prevent, detect, and respond to a security incident**.
- **Authentication and authorization procedures** must be sufficient to guarantee the **security of data and metadata at each stage of the workflow** (e.g. by requiring two-factor authentication for sensitive information).
- Evidence should include which **security policies** are in place to govern the security of all systems, including network security, intrusion checks, physical facility security, and passwords.
- If the response to Legal and Ethical (R04) includes references to holding **sensitive digital objects** then the response here should be **explicit about the additional measures** taken to protect this data and metadata.

Examples

“A central detection and automatic neutral-gas extinguishing system covers fire safety in addition to the machine-room layout, which is designed to provide fire protection for more than one hour. The four rooms are monitored separately with multiple sensors.”

“The solution utilizes only secure interfaces such as TLS 1.2 or above. All data in transit and at rest is encrypted with at least AES-256 or equivalent. The solution supports secure encrypted data storage both on and offsite which includes secure key management.”

“The repository has an IT operations handbook that also described disaster recovery procedures and responsibilities. This handbook is in line with the ISO 27001 information security standard and is audited by the head office of the repository.”

R14

Storage & Integrity

R14. The repository applies **documented processes** to ensure data and metadata **storage and integrity**.

In addition to maintaining 'archival' copies of digital objects, repositories need to **store data and metadata from the point of deposit, for curation and preservation, and for access by users**. For each storage location, measures should be in place to ensure that unintentional or unauthorised changes can be detected and correct versions of data and metadata recovered.

The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:

- Processes and documents to ensure that the repository staff have a clear **understanding of all storage locations and how they are managed**.
- The repository's **strategy for multiple copies**.
- The **risk management** techniques used to inform the strategy.
- Procedures for **handling and monitoring deterioration of storage media**.
- Procedures to ensure that data and metadata are **only deleted as part of an approved** and documented process.
- **Any checks (i.e. fixity checks)** used to verify that a digital object has not been altered or corrupted from deposit to use.

Storage and integrity measures should be covered here (R14) and not as part of Technical Infrastructure (R15) or Security (R16) responses. Details of how intentional changes to the data and metadata are logged should be covered under Provenance & Authenticity (R07).

Erläuterung aus der Guidance

- Die Antworten und Nachweise sollten Folgendes umfassen
 - alle **Speicherorte**, die Kurationsprozesse unterstützen,
 - die **Art und Weise, wie Daten und Metadaten in jeder Umgebung verwaltet werden**, und
 - das Vorhandensein von Prozessen zur **Überwachung und Verwaltung** von Änderungen an **der Speicherdokumentation**.
- Standardarbeitsanweisungen sollten so umfassend sein, dass **verschiedene Speicherverwalter zu weitgehend identischen Ergebnissen** gelangen, selbst wenn sie dieselben Aufgaben getrennt ausführen.
- Beispiele für Nachweise sind **Datenflussdiagramme**, die die Ablage-, Kurations- und Zugriffsorte (sowie etwaige Zugriffsbeschränkungen) abdecken.
- Für die Archivierung können die Nachweise z.B. Beschreibungen der **Mehrstandortvereinbarungen** (vor Ort, in der Nähe, außerhalb), der Kombination von Speichermedien und etwaiger **Redundanzen** (einschließlich Integrität durch Prüfsummen) umfassen.

Speicherung

“Plan for failures to happen in IT storage solutions. Failure rates in practice may well be higher than manufacturer statistics suggest.”

It is critical to understand the difference between standard IT storage solutions and the additional **needs of long-term preservation**. It is essential to be able to explain these differences to your IT department or storage service provider and to be able to **specify these requirements** when procuring a system or service. Standard storage systems are designed for digital objects that are in active use. While backup procedures are usually included, they generally do not meet the more stringent requirements to ensure long-term preservation of digital materials. Backup and digital preservation are not the same thing, and many IT departments or experts may not appreciate this.

Preservation storage systems require

- a **higher level of geographic redundancy**,
- stronger **disaster** recovery,
- longer-term **planning**,
- and most importantly **active monitoring of data integrity** in order to detect unwanted changes such as file corruption or loss.

Principles for using IT storage systems for digital preservation

1 Redundancy and diversity

- Make **multiple independent copies** of digital material and store these in **different geographic locations**.
- Use a combination of **online** storage systems and **offline** media.
- Use **different types of storage technology** to spread risk and achieve a balance of data safety, easy access and manageable cost.

2 Fixity, monitoring, repair

- Use **fixity** measures such as **checksums** to record and regularly monitor the integrity of each copy of the digital material.
- If corruption or loss is detected then use one of the other copies to create a **replacement**.
- Store fixity information** alongside the digital materials and **also in separate databases or systems**.

3 Technology and vendor watch, risk assessment, and proactive migrations

- Understand that storage technologies, products and services all have a short lifetime.
- Use technology watch to **assess** when **migrations** might be needed.
- Keep an eye on the **viability** of storage vendors or classes of storage solution.
- Be proactive** in migrating storage before digital material becomes at risk

4 Consolidation, simplicity, documentation, provenance and audit trails

- Minimise the proliferation** of legacy media types and storage systems used for preservation.
- Consolidate digital materials** onto the minimum number of preservation storage systems (subject to the redundancy requirements above).
- Document** how digital materials have been **acquired** and **transferred** into the storage systems as well as how the **storage systems** are set-up and operated.
- Use this to provide **audit information** on data authenticity.

Backup

3-2-1-1-0-Regel

3: Bewahren Sie mindestens drei Kopien Ihrer Daten auf

- mindestens zwei weitere Sicherungsdateien (besser: drei)
- Die sekundäre Datensicherung sollte nicht in unmittelbarer Nähe der primären Daten liegen

2: Speichern Sie Backups auf zwei verschiedenen Medien

- eine der Sicherungskopien auf einem internen Festplattenlaufwerk, die andere Kopie auf einem Wechselspeichermedium (externes Festplattenlaufwerk, Cloud-Speicher) zu sichern.
- Risiko streuen bei Ausfall eines Mediums oder Cyber-Angriff
- Alternativ:
 - primäres Backup auf den internen Festplattenlaufwerken eines physischen Servers
 - sekundäres Backup auf den internen Festplattenlaufwerken eines netzgebundenen Speichers (NAS), wobei die Festplattenlaufwerke beider Systeme von unterschiedlicher Marke, Größe und unterschiedlichem Typus sein sollten.

1: Bewahren Sie mindestens eine Sicherungskopie außerhalb des Standorts auf

- Mindestens eine Sicherungskopie sollte nicht an dem Ort vorgehalten werden, wo sich die Primärdaten und die Primärsicherung befinden (Brand, Überschwemmung, ...)

1: Speichern Sie mindestens eine Kopie offline

- mindestens eine Sicherungskopie offline aufzubewahren, somit getrennt vom Netzwerk und von jeglicher IT-Infrastruktur (Offline-Kopie mit einem Kodierungsschlüssel schützen)
 - Beispiele: rotierende externe USB-Festplatten, analoge Bänder und Objektspeicher mit Unveränderlichkeit als Funktionalität.

0: Vergewissern Sie sich, dass Ihre Backups fehlerfrei sind

- Backups sind nur so gut wie das Verfahren, mit dem sie geprüft werden.
 - Backups täglich überwachen
 - regelmäßigen Abständen Wiederherstellungstests

Storage: Redundancy and Backup

Backup – GESIS Beispiel

“The backup procedures are described in a Backup Concept (internal document, in German). GESIS follows a **3-2-1-1-0 rule** for backups, which is implemented with the help of a commercial backup software:

- 3 copies of all files of the organization (stored to three locations in Germany)
- 2 copies on different storage media
- 1 copy in a location far from the organization's site
- 1 copy offline and indestructible (encrypted, immutable backup in the cloud)
- 0 errors in backup (confirmed with **test data restorations**).

GESIS carries out daily incremental backups, full weekly backups, and full monthly backups with **different retention periods**.

Media refreshment is handled by GESIS' storage service provider (Wasabi). The outsource partner guarantees 99.999999999% object durability and has obtained **certification** for SOC-2 and ISO 27001 compliance”

Storage - in a nutshell:

- Kennen Sie Ihre Speicherlösung!
- Redundanz
- Back-Up
- Fixity Checks
- Verteilter Zugriff: Vermeiden Sie, dass eine einzelne Person Schreibzugriff auf alle Kopien der digitalen Inhalte hat.

Examples

“The repository uses checksums for all data.”

“Fixity for the archival storage is implemented on storage and on object level. Data is stored and backed-up automatically and the media are automatically monitored for block-level integrity.”

“When a new or amended deposit moves from the Ingest to the Archival Storage team a checksum (MD5) is generated for each file with the Archival Information Package (AIP).”

R15

Technical Infrastructure

R15. The repository is managed on **core infrastructural software and hardware** appropriate to the services it provides

- Repositories must operate on reliable and stable core infrastructure that maximises service availability. The details of technical infrastructure will vary widely across repositories.
- Responses and evidence should focus on demonstrating that the repository solution, including hardware and software is well managed and appropriate to the needs of the repository functions and the Designated Community of users.
- The response statement and evidence should include references to the following items:
 - The repository **software used for deposit, curation, preservation and access** management. Whether it is community supported, open source, or locally developed.
 - Any **IT service management** approach followed and the functions this approach specifies (e.g. systems documentation, software inventories, code repositories, infrastructure development planning).
 - Any international, community or other technical infrastructure **standards** (e. g. W3C, ISO, and IEEE) in place and how **compliance** is monitored.
 - The **version control** systems used for repository generated **software**.
 - Measures taken to ensure that **availability, bandwidth, and connectivity** are sufficient to meet the needs of the Designated Community.
 - Processes in place to **monitor and manage the need for technical change**, including in response to the changing needs of Preservation (R10), and Reuse (R13) by the Designated Community.

Erläuterung aus der Guidance

- **Technische Aspekte der Geschäftskontinuität, Notfallwiederherstellung und Nachfolgeplanung sind hier relevant**, ihre Verwaltung sollte jedoch unter „Kontinuität der Dienstleistungen“ (R03) behandelt werden. Diese Anforderung schließt Sicherheitsmaßnahmen (R16) und Speicherung und Integrität (R14) aus. Dateiformate und Metadatenschema-Informationen sollten unter „Hinterlegung und Bewertung“ (R08) und „Wiederverwendung“ (R13) aufgeführt werden. Nicht technische oder sicherheitsrelevante Standards sollten unter „Qualitätssicherung“ (R10) aufgeführt werden.
- Die Arbeitsabläufe und menschlichen Akteure, die Repository-Dienste bereitstellen, müssen durch eine **geeignete technologische Infrastruktur** unterstützt werden, die den Anforderungen der Designated Community entspricht und es dem Repository ermöglicht, sich von kurzfristigen Katastrophen zu erholen. Die Antworten und Nachweise sollten ein Verständnis des umfassenderen Ökosystems von Standards, Tools und Technologien für die Verwaltung und Aufbewahrung von (Forschungs-)Daten belegen. Es sollte klargestellt werden, dass die ausgewählten technischen Optionen den lokalen Anforderungen entsprechen, z. B. den von der Designated Community verwendeten Technologien oder einer Bandbreite, die ausreicht, um den prognostizierten Bedarf zu decken. Beispiele für relevante technische Standards sind W3C-, ISO- und IEEE-Standards.

In R15 soll die Institution nachweisen, dass ein Verständnis für das umfassendere Ökosystem von Standards, Tools und Technologien für die Verwaltung und Aufbewahrung von Forschungsdaten vorhanden ist.

Examples

“The repository has 5 servers at its disposal 3 of which are in a so called primary server room the remaining 2 are in a so called backup server room.”

“The repository is based on a Fedora Commons repository 3. It runs on Red Hat Enterprise Linux. Services to the Designated Community such as deposition and dissemination front-ends are implemented as separate services. For institutional depositors, there is a machine-machine deposit interface, based on the SWORD 2.0 protocol.”

Rückblick

Review – wie war das Arbeitsintervall ?

- Was hat **gut funktioniert**? Was möchte ich weiter so machen?
- Was hat **nicht so gut funktioniert**?
- Was könnte beim nächsten Arbeitsintervall **helfen**?
- Kann das **Measure** besser unterstützen?

CoreTrustSeal: Feedback

Nachtrag zu ESRA und CoRDI

- Die **einzelnen Rückmeldungen** bleiben natürlich anonym, wenn das von der Gruppe bzw. der einzelnen Institution gewünscht wird.
- Wir würden gerne die **Gruppe der gesamt teilnehmenden Institutionen nennen**. Wäre dies für euch in Ordnung? (So könnten wir im Vortrag bspw. skizzieren, aus welchen Disziplinen/Themenbereichen die teilnehmenden Institutionen/FDZ kommen, welche Daten durch die FDZ archiviert und bereitgestellt werden und die Größe der FDZ einordnen)

- Beitrag des Measures bei **ESRA Session im Juli 2025**:
 - Session „New developments in research data infrastructures“ organisiert von Daniel Fuß (LifBi)
<https://www.europeansurveyresearch.org/conf2025/sessions.php?sess=76>
 - „Promoting Professionalisation: A Case Study on Achieving CoreTrustSeal Certification and Improved Access to International and Interdisciplinary Data“

Fragen:

- Was ist eure **Motivation** für die Zertifizierung nach dem CoreTrustSeal?
 - Welche **Hindernisse bzw. Schwierigkeiten** seht ihr bei einer CoreTrustSeal-Zertifizierung?
 - Was sind eure **Erfahrungen / Einschätzungen**?
- Bitte um **formlose Rückmeldung bis Fr, 28.2.** per E-Mail an buck@dzhw.eu und kerstin.beck@gesis.org

Fragen/Anmerkungen?

11th Conference of the European
Survey Research Association (ESRA)

Utrecht, 16. July 2025

 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17238488>

Promoting Professionalisation:

A Case Study on Achieving CoreTrustSeal Certification and Improved Access to International and Interdisciplinary Data

Daniel Buck (DZHW) – *Presenting Author*

Dr Pascal Siegers (GESIS Leibniz-Institut für Sozialwissenschaften)

Kerstin Beck (GESIS Leibniz-Institut für Sozialwissenschaften)

Ute Hoffstätter (DZHW)

CoRDI: Poster presentation

Promoting Trust and Quality: A Case Study on the Challenges of Achieving CoreTrustSeal Certification by Social Science Data Centres

Creators: Beck, Kerstin; Hoffstätter, Ute; Buck, Daniel; Siegers, Pascal

Editors: Sure-Vetter, York; Groth, Paul

Achieving certification as a trustworthy digital repository represents a critical milestone in the development and professionalization of research data infrastructures. Such certification serves as a visible signal to users, policy makers, and funding organizations that a repository is capable of ensuring the long-term preservation of digital data and adheres to established professional standards for handling the challenges associated with sustaining access to re-search data over time. In this sense, trustworthy repository certification—such as the CoreTrustSeal (CTS)—is not merely a technical credential, but a strategic asset. It functions as both a quality assurance mechanism and a competitive advantage for attracting datasets from researchers, particularly in fields where data longevity and reusability are central to scientific progress. Beyond the external signaling function, the process of certification supports internal institutional development by encouraging infrastructures to formalize and document workflows, improve alignment with the FAIR Principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), and enhance collaboration....

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16735820> (25.09.2025)

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¹GESIS Leibniz Institut für Sozialwissenschaften
²Deutsches Zentrum für Hochschul- und Wissenschaftsforschung (DZHW)

Promoting Trust and Quality

A Case Study on the Challenges of Achieving CoreTrustSeal (CTS) Certification by Social Science Data Centres

Added value of CTS certifications

- Quality-assured, transparent repository workflows
- Compliance with funder or publisher requirements
- Recognized Internationally and across disciplines, helps archiving and offering international data!
- Review and revision of processes, documentation and policies based on expert feedback
- Improved internal communication
- Rely on the quality of data management and long-term archiving documented by CoreTrustSeal

Certificates of data repositories in Germany

Source: <https://www.rd3data.org/>, 18.06.2024, N=84

Case Study

The 39 Research Data Centers (RDC) accredited by the German Data Forum (RatSWD) were invited to a joint working group to apply for the CoreTrustSeal (most of them are small and medium sized repositories). Representatives of 7 RDCs participated at a first meeting, 4 have joined the monthly meeting of the working group:

- Discussion of CTS Requirements and Preparation of Templates addressing the requirements
- Peer review of draft versions of participants certification applications
- Additional workshop on specific topics with experts (e.g., long term availability)

Objective was to better understand motivations and obstacles to achieve CTS certification

Results

Major motivations

- Review and improve internal RDC operations for long term availability of data
- Closing gaps in process documentation
- International recognition and visibility of RDM capabilities
- Enhance transparency and credibility

Major obstacles

- Limited resources (no dedicated funding)
- Lack of support from the management
- RDC-external dependencies (IT department)
- High implementation effort and scope of change
- Uncertainty about practical benefits

Recommendations

- Joint efforts and mutual support through peer-review increase motivation and capability to address certification (→ better interpretation of requirements)
- Early involvement of relevant roles within the institutions is necessary (→ RDC-external dependencies)
- In a distributed archiving infrastructure with small, medium, and large RDCs, CTS should not only be considered in relation to the few largest RDCs.
- Management of research institutions should increase awareness to CTS as a means to deal with contemporary issues in RDM:
 - Data Security in case of IT security events
 - International cooperation in RDM
 - Trustworthiness of RDC across disciplines

KonsortSWD wird im Rahmen der NFDI durch die Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) gefördert – Projektnummer: 42494171

Ausblick

FIDELIS | Establishing A European Network of Trustworthy Digital Repositories (TDRs)

Dr. Jonas Recker, GESIS, 2025-09-17

FIDELIS Consortium

Consortium of **24 partners** across Europe, including **six scientific communities**: CESSDA (Social Sciences), CLARIN (Linguistics), ELIXIR (Biomedical Sciences), INRAE (Agri-food), ESRF (Physical Sciences) and DKRZ (Climate Science).

Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics

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DI PADOVA

01

Set up, develop, and operate a European network of trustworthy repositories that will support the development and growth of TDRs within the EOSC ecosystem

- Set up a lean governance structure to establish and operate the Network
- Build up a good membership base
- Develop and test the value proposition of the Network
- Provide common directionality and a common voice for digital repositories
- Develop a common understanding of legal requirements of TDRs
- Develop strategic partnerships and agreements with other initiatives

02

Foster harmonisation and interoperability across repositories to enable an EOSC federation of TDRs

- Develop a matrix of repository capabilities and characteristics
- Recommend standards, APIs and solutions to facilitate access to resources, foster interoperability and allow cross-repository services
- Facilitate the technical federation of repositories across EOSC

03

Strengthen the upskilling of repositories and expansion of the Network through an active training and support programme

- Identify training needs and support requests from digital repositories
- Develop a comprehensive training and mentoring programme
- Onboard new repositories in the Network
- Disseminate and demonstrate the added value of the Network and its activities across EOSC

FIDELIS Network of Trustworthy Digital Repositories

<https://eden-fidelis.eu/form/join-the-fidelis-network>

Become a provisional member

The Network's mission and activities

With the launch of the FIDELIS Network, we aim to support digital repositories in Europe to become and remain trustworthy over time. FIDELIS welcomes digital repositories that practice or aspire to practice [TRUST](#)-inspiring and [FAIR](#)-enabling ways of working to join the network.

FIDELIS Pilot Support Offers available!

- Starting 2026: FIDELIS open call launches (cascading grants)
- 2025: a pilot round exclusively for the provisional members of the FIDELIS Network.
- The 2025 pilot round includes three different support offers:
 - Enhancing Repository Transparency and Trustworthiness with TTRAM
 - Explorer track & Pathfinder track for CoreTrustSeal support
 - Opportunity to Develop your own FAIR EVA (Evaluator, Validator & Advisor) plugin
- Registration open between September 12th and September 26th
- For the pilot round, registration is on a first-come-first-served basis
- <https://eden-fidelis.eu/fidelis-pilot-support-offers>

Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix

- FIDELIS is developing the TTRAM to support reaching consensus about what “trustworthy digital repository” means in the EOSC context
- TTRAM is a tool to support
 - collecting information on repository activities & functions in a logical way
 - understanding the wide variety of types and practices across repositories
 - sharing structured information for consultation and use
 - a functional network of mutual support and aligned practice

L'Hours, H., Kleemola, M., Parkes, O., Recker, J., Duvaud, S., van Horik, R., Alaterä, T. J., Liberante, F., Conzett, P., Kaartinen, H., Bäckman, S., & Esteves, E. (2025). FIDELIS TTRAMatrix v00.02 Guide (v01.00). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15676189>

Referenzen

- CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. (2022). CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2023-2025 (V01.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051012>*
- CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. (2022). CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Digital Repositories Requirements 2023-2025 Extended Guidance (V01.00).* Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051096>
- CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. (2022). CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Data Repositories Requirements: Glossary 2023-2025 (V01.00).* Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051125>
- Digital Preservation Coalition (2024). *Digital Asset Register Toolkit, 1st Edition*, <http://www.doi.org/10.7207/dartool24-01>
- GESIS Data Services, 2024, "2027-03-28 - GESIS Data Services - CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2023-2025", <https://doi.org/10.34894/Y5YJGK>, DataverseNL, V1; 2027-03-28-GESISDataServices-CoreTrustSealRequirements2023-2025.pdf
- Hoffstätter, U., & Weber, A. (2024). Langzeitarchivierung von Forschungsdaten. Einführung in das Thema zu Daten der Sozial-, Verhaltens-, Bildungs- und Wirtschaftswissenschaften in Forschungsdatenzentren. KonsortSWD Working Paper Nr.9/2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10418834>
- Hoffstätter, U., & Beck, K. (2023). Workshopdokumentation: CoreTrustSeal: Erstveranstaltung. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10213806>.
- Liegmann, H. & Neuroth, H. (2010). Einführung. In H. Neuroth, A. Oßwald, R. Scheffel, S. Strathmann & K. Huth (Hrsg.), *nestor Handbuch: Eine kleine Enzyklopädie der digitalen Langzeitarchivierung*. Göttingen: Hülsbusch / Univ.-Verl. Göttingen.
- Recker, Jonas, Pascal Siegers, and Kerstin Beck. 2023. "Becoming a trustworthy digital preservation repository: Certification for data archives and research data centers." Meet the Experts - GESIS Online Talks, 2023-09-14. https://www.gesis.org/fileadmin/admin/Dateikatalog/Veranstaltungen/MeetTheExperts/recker_siegers_mte2023.pdf.
- Thibodeau, Kenneth. (2002). Overview of Technological Approaches to Digital Preservation and Challenges in Coming Years. In Council on Library and Information Resources (Ed.), *The state of digital preservation: An international perspective; conference proceedings, Documentation Abstracts, Inc. Institutes for Information Science, Washington, D.C., April 24-25, 2002* (pp. 4–31). CLIR. <https://www.clir.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/6/pub107.pdf>

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